

Comparing the Properties of Concrete (Experimental Data) Using Machine Learning Algorithms

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ABSTRACT:

Concrete is the most widely used construction material throughout the world. Extensive experiments are conducted every year to study the physical, mechanical, and chemical properties of concrete involving a hefty amount of money and time. This work focuses on the utilization of Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to predict various concrete properties for avoiding unnecessary experimentation. In this present work, six mechanical properties of concrete namely modulus of rupture, compressive strength, modulus of elasticity, Poisson's ratio, splitting tensile strength, and coefficient of thermal expansion are estimated by applying five different ML algorithms viz. Linear Regression, Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Gradient Boosting models on the Wisconsin concrete mixes database. Further, these ML models were evaluated to identify the most suitable model that can reliably predict the mechanical properties of concrete.

Keywords: Machine learning, compressive strength, Flexural strength, Split tensile strength.

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INTRODUCTION

ML is a computational technique destined to simulate human intelligence and speed up the computing procedure by means of continuous learning and evolution. ML techniques have been effectively implemented in several industries, including medical and biomedical equipment, entertainment, finance, and engineering applications. ML can be used in civil engineering in various fields such as infrastructure development, structural health monitoring, and predicting the mechanical properties of materials. This study has been undertaken to investigate the compressive strength, Flexural strength and split tensile strength of concrete of grade M30 and M40 in present investigation by laboratory and predicting the strength through Machine learning technique. Flexural strength and split tensile strength which establishes the concrete class, is one of the most crucial characteristics of concrete. To explore the time-dependent behavior of concrete strength, considering factors such as curing duration and age. Main aim is to compare the performance of different regression methods, such as linear regression, ridge regression, lasso regression, or

machine learning approaches like Random Forest and evaluate their suitability for concrete strength comparison and to find the accuracy of algorithms and regression.

OBJECTIVES OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The main objectives of the present work:

1. To design a mix of M30 and M40 grade of concrete specimen in laboratory and compare the strength of concrete of present investigation.
2. To analyse the data through machine learning the mechanical property such as compressive Strength, Flexural strength, Split tensile strength of concrete for M30 and M40 grade.
3. Compare the performance of different regression methods, such as linear regression, ridge regression, lasso regression, or machine learning approaches like Random Forest. Evaluate their suitability for concrete strength prediction.
4. To compare the original and predicted value through algorithms and regression.

LITERATURE REVIEW

General

A literature review on "Comparing the Properties of Concrete Using Machine Learning Algorithms" would involve examining existing research, studies, and publications related to the application of machine learning (ML) in analysing and predicting concrete properties. This chapter examines prior research on superplasticizer admixtures in concrete that is already available. Also discussed are the impact of these admixtures on the mechanical characteristics of freshly laid and hardened concrete. Also, machine learning approach introduced.

Literature Survey

Ultra-high performance concrete (UHPC) is an emerging cement-based material with high compressive and tensile strengths, ductility, and long-term durability. Some of the applications for which UHPC is well suited for are bridge piers, decks and deck-level connections between modular precast components, blast protection elements, high ductility designs, and repair and strengthening applications [4].

The main objective of [6] is to examine the variation according to cooling type of compressive and flexural strength of high-performance micro-concrete and ordinary micro-concrete at high temperatures. Compressive and flexural strengths of ordinary and high-performance micro-concrete exposed to high temperatures (200, 400, 600, 800, and 1000 °C) and cooled in various environments (in air and water) were obtained and the results compared.

In [8], an efficient implementation of machine learning models to predict compressive and tensile strengths of high-performance concrete (HPC) is presented. Four predictive algorithms including support vector regression (SVR), multilayer perceptron (MLP), gradient boosting regressor (GBR), and extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) are employed.

The experimental design of high-strength concrete (HSC) requires deep analysis to get the target strength. In this study, machine learning approaches and artificial intelligence python-based approaches have been utilized to predict the mechanical behaviour of HSC. The data to be used in the modelling consist of several input parameters such as cement, water, fine aggregate, and coarse aggregate in combination with a superplasticizer [1].

[11] proposed a BAS-RF model for forecasting the UCS of LWSCC. To construct the model, BAS was applied to search the optimum hyper-parameters of RF. The predictive performance of the BAS-RF model was evaluated on a dataset obtained in laboratory with 8 input variables

The main ingredients of concrete, a composite building material, are aggregate, cement, and water. Furthermore, to in addition to the basic components of regular concrete, high performance concrete contains additional cementitious materials, such as such as blast furnace slag and fly ash, and

chemical additives like superplasticizer. High-performance concrete is therefore a very It is challenging to model the behaviour present of complex material [7].

[10] calculated the consequences on strength of concrete when water- cement ratio is constant and the increase in slump occurs with the increase in amount of superplasticizer by percentage. The remaining research is done to examine the effects of various superplasticizer dosages under various curing regimes at 45°–50°C ambient field temperatures. This was accomplished by employing an ASTM C494 type A and F anionic melamine polycondensate non-toxic superplasticizer without chlorides to prepare a concrete mix at 20 MPa while maintaining all other parameters constant.

Analysing the concrete's properties requires knowledge of its compressive strength. To determine whether the given concrete mixture satisfies the requirements, the compressive strength is required. The required standards for compressive strength must be met for the construction to be sustainable. Models for machine learning have proven to be a very useful tool for problem analysis across many domains [3].

[9] compares the accuracy of various ML models in predicting CS, including non-ensemble models (Multiple Linear Regressor, Support Vector Regressor) and ensemble models (AdaBoost Regressor, Random Forest Regression, XGBoost Regressor, and Bagging Regressor).

The kind, characteristics, and composition of the materials that make up Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC) determine the material's compressive strength. Using clever algorithms, like the Artificial Neural Network (ANN), to create a predictive model that fits into an experimental dataset is frequently necessary to empirically capture this relationship [2].

Extremely cold or oceanic conditions call for high-durability concrete, which makes concrete mix design crucial and challenging. In order to effectively predict concrete durability and optimise the concrete mix ratio, a hybrid intelligent framework for multi-objective optimisation based on random forest (RF) and the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm version II (NSGA-II) is developed in this study [5].

METHODOLOGY

General

This present investigation started with reading current things happening in civil engineering and after that deciding the area or field of thesis present investigation want to work on. After arrangement in materials, sampling of the material starts. Then testing of samples is done taking all the precautions and follow procedures of experiments properly and accurately.

Materials

1. Cement
2. Sand
3. Coarse Aggregate
4. Fine Aggregate
5. Water
6. Super Plasticizer
7. BONDING AGENT

Testing of Materials and Specimens

1. Cement

Figure1. Physical Test of Cement

2. Sand

Figure2. Physical Test of Sand

3. Aggregate

Figure3. Physical Test of Aggregate

Concrete Mix Design in I.S. Code Practice

In the context of civil engineering and construction, concrete mix design is a process of selecting suitable proportions of ingredients to produce concrete with desired properties in both the fresh and hardened states. The mix design is typically based on various factors such as the strength

requirements, workability, durability, and availability of materials. In India, the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) has established the guidelines for concrete mix design through the Indian Standard (I.S.) codes, the relevant code for concrete mix design in India is IS 10262:2019.

Machine Learning Techniques

Machine learning (ML) is a field of artificial intelligence that focuses on developing algorithms and models that allow computers to learn from data and make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed. There are various techniques within machine learning, and they can be broadly categorized into three main types: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning.

Regression Models & Recommended Systems

1. *Linear regression* A variable's value can be predicted using linear regression analysis based on the value of another variable. The dependent variable is the one that you wish to be able to predict. The independent variable is the one you are using to forecast the value of the other variable. For concrete to be produced at full strength, role was adequate. Using one or more independent variables that best predict the value of the dependent variable, this type of analysis calculates the coefficients of the linear equation. A straight line or surface that minimises the differences bet present investigational the expected and actual output values is fitted by linear regression. The "least squares" approach is used by some basic linear regression calculators to find the best-fit line for a set of paired data. Next, using Y as the independent variable, you estimate the value of X, the dependent variable.

2. *Ridge regression*, a linear regression technique called ridge regression is intended to deal with situations in which the predictor variables show high correlation or high collinearity. Conventional regression models can produce inconsistent or unreliable results when multicollinearity is present.

3. *LASSO regression*, which is also referred to as L1 regularisation, is a widely employed method in statistical modelling and machine learning for predicting and estimating the relationships bet present investigational variables. Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator is referred to as LASSO. LASSO regression's main objective is to strike a balance bet present investigational model accuracy and simplicity. LASSO is especially helpful for feature selection since it can recognise and eliminate redundant or irrelevant variables automatically

4. *The Algorithm of Random Forest*: A present investigational-liked supervised machine learning algorithm for classification and regression issues in machine learning is the Random Forest Algorithm. As present investigation all know, a forest is made up of many trees, and the more trees it has, the more robust it is. Similarly, an algorithm's accuracy and capacity to solve problems increase with the number of trees in the Random Forest. . A classifier called Random Forest uses multiple decision trees on different dataset subsets and averages them to increase the dataset's predictive accuracy. Its foundation is the idea of ensemble learning, which is the process of merging several classifiers to solve a challenging issue and enhance the model's functionality.

Essentials

Present goal is to apply machine learning to the design of concrete mixes in present study. Present investigation would like to construct a regression that can estimate the compressive strength of the concrete mix based on a large number of tested concrete mix recipes. More specifically, the amount of each of the present major constituents of a concrete mix—cement, fine and coarse aggregate, water—is used in the regression to estimate the strength of the concrete.

Figure 4. Flow Chart of the Present Investigation

RESULTS BY MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH

After testing the characteristics strengths of concrete, we put the dataset in machine learning technique to apply different regressions and algorithms to predict the accuracy of our data and compare the predicted data with original values. The results of different regression methods are shown below.

Compressive Strength

concrete strength					
Regression methods	predicted score	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R2
linear	0.677	2.86	12.99	3.6	67.73
rigid	0.68		12.76	3.57	
lasso	0.677		12.97	3.6	
random forest	0.796		8.2	2.86	

Figure 5. Results of All Regression Models of Compressive Strength

	predicted_values	original_values
19	42.48	29.25
49	42.48	40.50
48	42.48	40.50
12	42.48	40.50
44	42.48	45.00
5	42.48	29.70
17	42.48	45.00
52	42.48	45.00
3	42.48	29.70
32	42.48	40.50

Figure 6. Original Vs Predicted Value in Final Regression Model

Flexural Strength

flexural strength					
Regression methods	predicted score	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R2
linear	0.69	0.16	0.031	0.17	69.54
rigid	0.58		0.42	0.2	
lasso	-0.281		0.131	0.17	
random forest	0.87		0.013	0.11	

Figure 7. Results of all regression models of Flexural Strength

	predicted_values	original_values
0	4.564	4.02
1	4.564	4.02
8	4.564	4.70
5	4.564	4.70
3	4.564	4.70
13	4.564	4.70

Figure 8. Original Vs Predicted Value in Final Regression Model

Split Tensile Strength

split strength					
Regression methods	predicted score	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R2
linear	0.82	0.2	0.06	0.236	82.52
rigid	0.79		0.06	0.25	
lasso	-0.28		0.41	0.24	
random forest	0.84		0.052	0.23	

Figure 9. Results of All Regression Models of Split Tensile Strength

	predicted_values	original_values
0	4.212	3.3
1	4.212	3.3
8	4.212	4.5
5	4.212	4.5
3	4.212	4.5
13	4.212	4.5

Figure 10. Original Vs Predicted value in Final Regression Model

CONCLUSION

In this study, a prediction model for the strengths of concrete with and without superplasticizers was developed using 4 supervised learning methods from machine learning to address the high-dimensional complex non-linear relationship between present investigational the superplasticizer mixing design and the strength of concrete. Using dataset, the prediction of concrete's compressive, flexural and split tensile strength was carried out with great accuracy. After conducting a statistical analysis of the dataset, a correlation analysis was performed. This study demonstrates a relationship between present investigational the strength of concrete in tension and compression. Using regression analysis in concrete we have compared the predicted value with the values calculated from the tests performed.

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